

Telephone Triage in an Emergency Central: Implementation Analysis

Frieda Saicla Barros
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do
Paraná Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-3962-1192

Jane Sescatto
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do
Paraná Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0000-9912-350X

Henrique Cunha Carvalho
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do
Paraná Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0003-0806-4132

Abstract - The Manchester Triage System (MTS) is the most widely used system in emergency services in several countries. The risk classification and triage sectors have been crucial in organizing emergency services, enabling a more efficient and humanized flow. In Curitiba-Paraná, the Manchester Risk Classification System (MRCS) was implemented in Emergency Care Units (UPA) in 2012 to improve the quality of care provided to the population. With technological advancements, the need to implement telephone triage at the Mobile Emergency Care Service (SAMU 192) Regulatory Center was identified. This article aims to demonstrate the progress of the implementation process methodology at the SAMU 192 Central, highlighting the main challenges nursing professionals face when using this technological arrangement. A quantitative analysis covering the period from January to May 2025, corresponding to the implementation of this risk classification tool for Telephone Triage and Advice (TTA), based on the Manchester Triage System – Telephone Triage and Advice (MTS TTA), shows that of the 117.066 calls, (10.38%) were "trauma" calls, totaling 12.159, and (70.70%) represented "clinical primary calls," totaling 82.771. Of the calls, 11.660 were classified using the TTA methodology, representing 9.96%, with an average of 292 classifications per nurse. The results show that implementing Telephone Triage and Counseling (TTA) at the SAMU 192 Center demonstrates significant potential for accurately defining clinical priority levels. The effectiveness of remote triage needs to be continually measured, especially concerning clinical outcomes, service resolution, and user satisfaction. Refining operational and care strategies, focusing on qualified listening and accurate risk classification, will optimize the allocation of available resources.

Keywords - emergency services, classification, telephone triage.

I. INTRODUCTION

The high demand for emergency services has forced healthcare managers to restructure healthcare organization models. Implementing triage systems is essential for organizing flows and prioritizing cases based on clinical severity in hospital and pre-hospital care [1].

The Manchester Triage System (MTS) is the most widely used system in emergency services. In Brazil, the Unified Health System (SUS) implements the Risk

Classification Reception (ACCR), a fundamental guideline of the National Humanization Policy (PNH), aimed at improving care in the SUS [2].

Risk classification and triage are crucial in organizing emergency department care, enabling a more efficient and humanized flow. This approach is essential to ensuring that patients receive appropriate care based on the severity of their conditions, especially in high-demand settings [3].

The National Emergency Care Policy, reformulated by the Ministry of Health in 2010, established risk-based reception as a fundamental guideline for improving care at the healthcare system's entry points [4]. This policy advocates that care quality and responsiveness should form the basis of care processes and flows throughout the Emergency Network, promoting the organization of services based on clinical severity and user needs, rather than simply on a first-come, first-served basis.

The maximum times for first medical care in an emergency are indicated by colors, with red determining an emergency condition, and care must be immediate; orange discriminating conditions of high urgency, whose time for care must be ≤ 10 minutes; yellow suggests urgency, defining care within ≤ 60 minutes; those attended in green are of low urgency and care can occur in up to ≤ 120 minutes; those in blue, in turn, are considered non-urgent and their care is indicated to occur within ≤ 240 minutes [5].

The municipality of Curitiba, Paraná state, implemented the Manchester Risk Classification System (SCRM) in 2012 at Emergency Care Units (UPA) to improve the quality of care provided to the population.

With technological advancements, the need to implement telephone triage as a risk classification tool at the Mobile Emergency Care Service (SAMU 192) Regulatory Center was identified. The Manchester Triage System Telephone Triage and Advice (MTS TTA) is a clinical risk assessment tool used worldwide as a telephone triage tool, primarily in ambulance services [6]. It aims to ensure priority care and an appropriate plan through remote triage assessment. The situations identified by the triage nurse as lower acuity enable safe referral of patients to alternative healthcare services, such as primary care or outpatient care, when appropriate [7].

The main objective of this article is to demonstrate the progress of implementing this methodology at the SAMU 192 Center, highlighting the main challenges nursing professionals face when using this technological arrangement. That way, it is hoped that the article will provide insights into implementing a risk classification tool at a SAMU 192 Center.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is a quantitative analysis covering the period from January to May 2025, corresponding to the implementation of Telephone Triage and Advice (TTA), based on the Manchester Triage System – Telephone Triage and Advice (MTS TTA), at a Mobile Emergency Care Service (SAMU 192) Regulatory Center in the municipality of Curitiba.

The usability of the risk classification tool used by nursing professionals is achieved through access to the computerized system available at the SAMU 192 central. The SAMU 192 plays a role in this process, serving not only the Curitiba population but also users from other municipalities in the Metropolitan Region. This scope reinforces the importance of an efficient triage system capable of responding to demands quickly and safely based on the clinical severity of the cases.

Table 1. Distribution of the registered Flowchart and Discriminators [6]

Flowchart	Discriminator
Falls	Intense Pain
Discomfort in Adults	Sudden Onset
Behavior Change	Significant Aggression or Agitation
Seizures	Convulsing
Problems in Extremities	Intense Pain
Fainting	Non-Reactive
Chest pain	Precordial or Heart Pain
Dyspnea in Adults	Inadequate Breathing
Abdominal pain in Adults	Intense Pain
Dyspnea in Adults	Inadequate Breathing

Source: GBCR, 2018.

The SAMU 192 central nurse, through the TTA, collects basic information, which will dictate the selection of the presentation flowchart. After choosing the flowchart, questioning techniques are used to obtain information to decide the clinical priority to be assigned, according to the discriminator. In the phone screening and counseling, the healthcare professional must be prepared to cover all possibilities, based on the information contained in the flowcharts. After choosing the flowchart, questionnaire techniques are used to decide the priority to be assigned,

using the discriminator. The flowchart discriminators (see Tables 1, 2 and 3) are defined to determine clinical priority.

Table 2. Example of a specific discriminator in Telephone Screening [6]

Discriminator	Questions	Definition
Precordial or cardiac pain	Where is the pain? Have you ever had pain like this? How would you describe the pain? Does it affect your arm or neck?	Pain in the middle of the chest, often tight or heavy, that may radiate to the left arm or neck. It may be associated with sweating, nausea, fainting, and/or epigastric pain.

Table 3. Example of a specific discriminator for temporary counseling in telephone triage [6]

Discriminator	Temporary counseling
Convulsing	Place the patient in the safe lateral position. Loosen clothing. Do not attempt to put anything in the mouth.

III. RESULTS

The analysis refers to the period from January to May 2025, and of the total of 117.066 calls, 10.38% are equivalent to “traumas”, totaling 12.151 and 70.70% represent “clinical primary”, totaling 82.765 calls. The total calls, 11.660, were classified using the TTA methodology, representing 9.96%.

The flowcharts used in 14.9% of the 11.660 classifications performed during the period were analyzed, according to the TTA methodology, as demonstrated in Table 4 related to criteria and priority. During this period, 40 nurses worked with an mean of 292 classifications per nurse.

Table 4. Classification according to priority

Priority	Results
RED (immediate treatment)	“Convulsions” was the most used flowchart in the total of 431 classifications, with 19.28% of notifications in red, and the “Apparent Drunkenness” flowchart was the least used, with 42 records, equivalent to 1,88%.
ORANGE (brief treatment)	“Discomfort in Adults” was the most used flowchart in a total of 806 classifications, with 14.42% of notifications in orange. “Seizures” was the least used flowchart, with 177 records, equivalent to 3.17%.
BLUE (not urgent)	“Discomfort in Adults” was the most used flowchart, registering 15 classifications, with 46.88% of notifications in blue. “Overdose and poisoning” was the least used flowchart, with one record, equivalent to 31.3%.
GREEN (elective treatment)	“Discomfort in Adults” was the most used flowchart, registering 243 classifications, with 25.18% of notifications in green. “Seizures” was the least used flowchart, with 25 records (equivalent to 2.59%).

The evaluation followed the Manchester Triage System protocols, which assign clinical priority through color coding, according to the degree of urgency identified in the flowchart selected during triage. Telephone triage demonstrates good results when performed correctly. For risk classification in emergency systems to be effective, nursing professionals must receive appropriate training, as one of their key skills is obtaining the most relevant information over the phone in the shortest possible time for decision-making.

The patient's presenting complaint generally defines the flowchart. The discriminator indicates the characteristic that differentiates patients from one another [6]. The knowledge of risk classification is a fundamental element in healthcare professionals' work processes, especially in emergency services. This classification guides the prioritization of care based on the patient's clinical severity, rather than on a first-come, first-served basis, as recommended by the SUS guideline [7].

Clinical judgment informed by pertinent information obtained during telephone referral can reliably anticipate short-term outcomes, enabling early risk stratification in the prehospital phase and supporting more efficient management of patient flow in the emergency department, also found by van Dam et al. [8]. This analysis sought to understand the distribution of clinical priorities assigned in remote triage and assess the tool's effectiveness in risk stratification for appropriate patient referral. When the patient is far from the triage, the temporary counseling provided by the nurse during the telephone consultation often helps promote recovery or prevent clinical deterioration until appropriate medical resources arrive.

IV. COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Statement of Informed Consent

The study used data already collected from the e-health system report 196, and informed consent was waived as it did not involve risks to the participants.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The results presented here are a preliminary look at the impact of an effective technological tool for risk classification. People who remain at home or are safely referred for care according to clinical priority can benefit from care management, user satisfaction, and better resource management. This analysis, however, doesn't end with the initial results. It's crucial to continue monitoring and evaluating the impacts of TTA on patient care.

The effectiveness of this remote triage technology needs to be continually measured, especially concerning clinical outcomes, service resolution, and patient satisfaction. Furthermore, it's necessary to refine operational and care strategies, focusing on improving listening skills, accurate risk classification, and allocating available resources, ensuring a balance between patient safety and efficient healthcare management. Only with this systematic monitoring will it be possible to consolidate TTA as a strategic tool within medical regulation, contributing to more agile, safe care that focuses on the real needs of the population.

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Author: Jane Sescatto
Institute: University Technological Federal of Paraná - UTFPR
Street: Rua Vicente Geronasso, 388
City: Curitiba/Paraná
Country: Brazil
Email: jsescatto@sms.curitiba.pr.gov.br